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HOW CITIZENS' VOTES CAN THREATEN LOCAL HERPETOFAUNA? A STORY FROM THE BALKANS

SUMMARY

After the breakage of the Balkan country Socialistic Federative Republic (SFR) of Yugoslavia, the status of local herpetofauna and regional biodiversity conservation didn't improve much. With the changes of the national political systems, citizens of the ex-Yugoslavia also had to face aggressive urbanization, increase of deforestation, loss of small water bodies and destruction of the mountain rivers - all four negative for survival of local amphibian and reptile populations in the entire Balkans. Increase of aggressive urbanisation resulted in the destruction of the network of small green areas in the cities, crucial for the survival of local herpetofauna in residential areas. Intensification of forests' exploitation and the threatening regional status of the small water bodies increased probability of cumulative negative effect on populations of local herpetofauna. Recently, out-of-river small hydropower plants (SHPP) have spread throughout the Balkans, revealing questionable capacity of national governments to fight ecological crisis. Recent mini-review about impact of SHPP on the Balkan herpetofauna showed that there are species which rely on small lotic aquatic systems in the hilly/mountain parts. Even these are just 28% and 12% of overall amphibian and reptile species in the region, respectively, some of them are very common and widespread; therefore, the fact that almost 5000 Balkan rivers would be devastated suggests that the most of populations of these species could be jeopardised. All these issues seem to be the consequence of wrong political choices made by citizens of the Balkan countries and of their inability to choose a political option which will support biodiversity conservation. The take-home message may be that it seems urgent to start addressing local conservation issues in Europe, before it becomes too late for the recovery of European biodiversity hotspots such as the Balkan Peninsula.

Key words: Balkans Peninsula, former Yugoslavia, Reptiles, Amphibians, current threats.

RIASSUNTO

Come possono i voti dei cittadini minacciare la fauna locale? Una storia dai Balcani. Dopo la rottura della Repubblica Socialista Federativa (SFR) di Jugoslavia, nei Balcani, lo stato dell'erpeto-

fauna locale e la conservazione della biodiversità regionale non sono migliorate molto. Con i cambiamenti dei sistemi politici nazionali i cittadini dell'ex Jugoslavia hanno dovuto far fronte a un'urbanizzazione aggressiva, all'aumento della deforestazione, alla perdita di piccoli corpi idrici e alla distruzione dei fiumi montani, con conseguenze negative per la sopravvivenza delle popolazioni locali di anfibi e rettili. L'incremento dell'urbanizzazione aggressiva ha portato alla distruzione della rete di piccole aree verdi delle città, cruciali per la sopravvivenza dell'erpetofauna locale nelle aree residenziali. L'intensificazione dello sfruttamento delle foreste e la minaccia occorsa ai piccoli corpi idrici hanno accresciuto la probabilità di produrre effetti negativi cumulativi sulle popolazioni di anfibi e rettili a livello locale. In tempi recenti, piccole centrali idroelettriche (*SHPP*) si sono diffuse in tutti i Balcani, rivelando una discutibile capacità dei governi nazionali di combattere la crisi ecologica. Una recente mini-revisione sull'impatto dell'*SHPP* sull'erpetofauna balcanica ha mostrato che ci sono specie la cui esistenza dipende da piccoli sistemi acquatici lotici delle zone collinari/montane. Queste rappresentano rispettivamente solo il 28% e il 12% delle specie complessive di anfibi e rettili presenti nella regione, alcune di esse sono molto comuni e diffuse; pertanto, il fatto che quasi 5000 fiumi balcanici sarebbero stati devastati suggerisce che la maggior parte delle popolazioni di queste specie potrebbe essere messa a repentaglio. Tutti questi problemi sembrano essere la conseguenza di scelte politiche errate fatte dai cittadini dei paesi balcanici e della loro incapacità di operare una scelta politica a sostegno della conservazione della biodiversità. Il messaggio che se ne può ricavare potrebbe essere che vi è l'urgenza di iniziare ad affrontare a livello Comunitario i problemi di conservazione locale che si presentano in Europa, prima che sia troppo tardi affinché vengano salvaguardati a livello europeo gli *hotspot* di biodiversità come la Penisola Balcanica.

Parole chiave: Penisola Balcanica, ex Jugoslavia, Anfibi, Rettili, attuali minacce.

INTRODUCTION

The world is facing global biodiversity crisis which is not a recent issue; it has existed since decades. To slow down the process of extinction of species and loss of habitats, the Convention on Biological Diversity (CBD) was promoted in 1992, in the city of Rio de Janeiro. It was an attempt to make an "easy to read" and efficient document aiming to help to understand that biodiversity cannot be constrained by political boundaries into independent geographical patches. Article 3. of CBD mentions that "States have, in accordance with the Charter of the United Nations and the principles of international law, the sovereign right to exploit their own resources pursuant to their own environmental policies, and the responsibility to ensure that activities within their jurisdiction or control do not cause damage to the environment of other States or of areas beyond the limits of national jurisdiction" (<https://www.cbd.int/doc/legal/cbd-en.pdf>). Also, in Article 8., a number of activities related to protection of national biodiversity was listed, among them "(a) Establish a system of protected areas or areas where special measures need to be taken to conserve biological diversity; (b) Develop, where necessary, guidelines for the selection, establishment and management of protected areas or areas where special measures need to be taken to conserve bio-

logical diversity; (c) Regulate or manage biological resources important for the conservation of biological diversity whether within or outside protected areas, with a view to ensuring their conservation and sustainable use; (d) Promote the protection of ecosystems, natural habitats and the maintenance of viable populations of species in natural surroundings; (e) Promote environmentally sound and sustainable development in areas adjacent to protected areas with a view to furthering protection of these areas”.

The sovereignty of every state who signed the Convention to manage its own biodiversity would sound nice to national governments, but how many countries in the world can exploit “national” biodiversity without negatively influencing the biodiversity of the neighboring countries? Those in the Balkan Peninsula are not geographically isolated. These countries have been connected not just by history, but by sharing the same natural resources (mountains, lowlands, watersheds, lakes, and the sea). Political transition experienced by the countries previously united in the Socialistic Federative Republic (SFR) Yugoslavia, as well as by others post-socialistic countries in the region, have shown that the process of “democratisation” would not inevitably guarantee improvement of national biodiversity conservation. Are the majority of voters capable to recognise which political option has the ability to improve their wealth respecting biodiversity conservation? How much these voters understand the importance of biodiversity conservation? When the national biodiversity conservation is jeopardised? Is it exclusively a national issue?

Here, examples of conservation challenges of amphibians and reptiles, either within the former SFR Yugoslavia or within the Balkan Peninsula will show how much the efforts to strengthen awareness and ecological knowledge in the region (by preparing and sharing documents, organising workshops, trainings, conferences, study visits etc. for national government representatives and responsible institutions... see in EURONATURE *et al.* (2004), increased the quality of biodiversity conservation in this area.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

The Balkan Peninsula is one of the three southern biodiversity hot spots in Europe, at least regarding its genetic diversity. In comparison to other two southern refugia – the Italian and Iberian peninsulas – the Balkan Peninsula has been a more dynamic transitional zone for the species migrating from West to the East and *vice versa* (see CRNOBRNJA-ISAILOVIĆ, 2007). It is predominantly a mountainous area, with the Outer Dinarides along the eastern coast of the Adriatic Sea, replaced to the South by the Scardo-Pindus moun-

tains along the Ionian Sea, and the Inner Dinarids from Slovenia on the North-West to the Morava and Vardar River valleys in Serbia and North Macedonia, respectively. The Balkan Mountains are distributed mostly in Bulgaria, part of the Carpathians includes Eastern Serbia, the Rhodope Mountains occur in parts of Bulgaria, North Macedonia and Greece, and there are isolated summits, including the Olympus, Pelion and Ossa mountains in Greece.

The SFR Yugoslavia was made up of Slovenia, Croatia and the countries of the “Western Balkan”, with the exception of Albania. Few recently published or “in press” literature data which summarizing new threats to the herpetofauna in part of the Balkans or throughout the Balkans were used as a material for this study; but the problems raised here are common to the whole world. The case studies from the Republic of Serbia included a) a communication at the conference on the differences in herpetofauna richness between two large cities (CRNOBRNJA-ISAILOVIĆ *et al.*, 2016) related to aggressive urbanisation that started along with the political transition after the year 2000; b) few studies on the importance of maintaining complex forest ecosystems for the well-being of local populations of some reptile species (STOJADINOVIĆ *et al.*, 2017; ĆOROVIĆ *et al.*, 2019; NIKOLIĆ *et al.*, 2020), and c) a study suggesting how forest cover reduction could impact the local population of common amphibian species (JOVANOVIĆ *et al.*, 2020). The recent status and threats to small water bodies used by amphibians as breeding sites were considered in a chapter of the monograph on small water bodies in the Western Balkans (CRNOBRNJA-ISAILOVIĆ *et al.*, 2022). Finally, in the mini review, the proliferation of “out-of-river” small hydropower plants throughout the Balkan Peninsula was considered an emerging problem for the local populations of some species of amphibians and reptiles (CRNOBRNJA-ISAILOVIĆ *et al.*, 2021).

RESULTS

Aggressive urbanisation

PERIC & D’HONDT (2020) revealed that territorial capital in the Balkans is seriously threatened due to the abuse of legal procedures, public disinterest and the politicisation of planning. Based on available literature data and personal observations, a brief comparison of the distribution of amphibians and reptiles before and after the year of democratic changes in Serbia (year 2000) was conducted for two of the three largest Serbian cities: Belgrade, the capital, and Niš, a regional center. The analysis conducted in Belgrade showed that only 8% and 17% of its total number of amphibian and reptile

species, respectively, inhabited the city center after year 2000 (CRNOBRNJA-ISAILOVIĆ *et al.*, 2016) while 27% and 33% of the total number of amphibians and reptiles, respectively, of Niš were found in the city center. Aggressive urbanisation in Belgrade began after period of civil wars and was reflected in a rapid replacement of single-family homes with green backyards by densely distributed buildings with no green corridors and/or green areas in between. This process, also called „investors' urbanism“, continues, despite objections from environmental professionals and civil organisations.

Increased deforestation

According to the national data compilation by VUKOVIĆ & VUKOVIĆ-MANDIĆ (2018), forests cover significant portions of the Western Balkans – ranging from 29% in Serbia to 60% in Montenegro. Despite ongoing issues related to climate change (temperature rise, prolonged droughts, severe floods) and knowledge about ecosystem services provided by forests, their exploitation is showing an increasing trend, at least in some of those countries. In Serbia, for example, deforestation is also taking place due to the aggressiveness of tourist town planning and the spread of urban areas (while the total number of citizens in the country is decreasing). A look at a few studies reveals the connection between local forest habitat systems and the ecological needs of some reptile species (STOJADINOVIĆ *et al.*, 2017; ĆOROVIĆ *et al.*, 2019; NIKOLIĆ *et al.*, 2020) and on canopy as important shelter during the breeding season of some common amphibian species (JOVANOVIĆ *et al.* 2020).

Loss of small water bodies

An overview on the status of small water bodies (SWB) as last refugia for amphibian species in the Western Balkan countries showed that they are silently disappearing, due to both anthropogenic impact (intensive habitat alterations such as conversion to the agricultural land, be it the construction of highways, the opening of new mines for the exploitation of rare or essential minerals, deforestation, etc.), or natural causes (succession and/or climate change) (CRNOBRNJA-ISAILOVIĆ *et al.*, 2022). The conservation of the SWB is, in many cases, linked to the socio-economic status of the people, i.e. the stimulation of local stakeholders to continue with the traditional practices of agriculture and livestock, including the maintenance of the SWB, and to their continuous education on the importance of SWB for the preservation of high values of local biodiversity. In addition, the natural SWB should be regularly monitored for threats; any disturbance detected, referring to both an unusual change in the water level or a decline in occurring populations and / or species, should be adequately mitigated. Although the value of SWB is

already known in Europe, it appears that decision makers in the Balkan countries have not been educated or, what could be more efficient, trained by implementing appropriate legal acts to care for these important habitats.

Destruction of the mountain rivers

A few years ago, small out-of-river hydropower plants (SHPP) began to proliferate throughout the Balkans, revealing the questionable ability of national governments to combat the ecological crisis. Recent mini-review about impact of SHPP on Balkan herpetofauna recalled that there are species of amphibians and reptiles in the hilly/mountain parts that depend on small lotic aquatic systems (CRNOBRNJA-ISAILOVIĆ *et al.*, 2021). These also represent only 28% and 12% of the total number of amphibian and reptile species in the region, respectively, some of which are very widespread. Therefore, the fact that nearly 5,000 Balkan rivers would be devastated suggests that many of these species would be regionally endangered. This reveals a profound conflict between scientific knowledge and profit, and a paradox of ignoring biodiversity conservation by applying theoretically sustainable practices. Even hydropower in EU is now longer recognised as a „sustainable“ source, there are still investors in the Balkans, at least in Serbia, who profit from the construction of SHPP that apparently disturb local environmental values and local biodiversity. Appeals from local communities and even national experts are ignored.

CONCLUSIONS

Both amphibians and reptiles are globally highly threatened animal groups (ANTHONY *et al.*, 2008; BÖHM *et al.*, 2013). Europe is a small area but under severe pressure from an industrially developed human population and with many challenges for its biodiversity. One third of the European amphibian and reptile species inhabit the Balkan Peninsula (SPEYBROECK *et al.*, 2020). Freshwaters and forests in the Balkan countries, which are important habitats for both of these vertebrate groups, are treated by key stakeholders as free capital that must be easily converted into their own economic advantage. From the beginning of the democratic changes until today, the citizens of some Balkan countries have not shown interest / knowledge / capacity to choose / elect a true „green“ political option. This suggests that loss of biodiversity in the Balkan Peninsula, and thus the loss of some essential habitats for its amphibians and reptiles, should not be a purely national issue. Biodiversity is global responsibility.

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